

Research Article

eBook Oasis: A Unified Platform for Revolutionizing the Digital Book Market

Zalina Kemat¹

¹ Kolej Poly-Tech MARA Batu Pahat, Sri Gading, Batu Pahat, Johor
zalina@gapps.kptm.edu.my;

* Correspondence: zalina@gapps.kptm.edu.my; +6011-14806096.

Abstract: eBook Oasis is an electronic marketplace where you can easily buy and sell e-books to make it more user-friendly for buyers and sellers alike. This paper will explore what eBook Oasis is all about, its distinguishing characteristics, and how it can be promoted in the fast-growing world of digital publishing. Built through an agile process model, eBook Oasis has developed a cohesive interface linking avid readers with self-published authors, thus bridging the market gap. And by improving accessibility issues, equity concerns, and sustainability issues in the eBook digital realm, eBook Oasis's mission is to foster affordability and universal access. From this study, some of the problems associated with traditional print books, like accessibility issues, high price tags, or adverse effects on the environment, have been presented and then evidenced as an unlimited source of money-saving alternatives. As an answer to these rising online demands for digital solutions; including interactive features that engage a whole community while providing reliable assistance services online for its users as well as ensuring their stability over time, there are still so many more things that need to be done within it, like analysing who will use it before launching the product, especially since this type of innovation has not yet been seen anywhere else.

Keywords: digital book market, self-publishing authors, Agile methodology, integrated interface, traditional print books, digital solutions

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1. INTRODUCTION

The digital book market has grown significantly, with an increasing number of users and authors choosing e-books as their primary medium (Gilbert, 2015). In Malaysia, the number of e-book readers has continuously increased, with e-book readership predicted to reach 7.5 million people by 2029, with user penetration expected to be 16.7% in 2024 and 20.5% in 2029 (Statista, 2023) proving an obvious pattern of e-publishing among Malaysian writers (Azuar, 2023). Globally, e-book publication has increased substantially, with millions of new titles released each year (Statista, 2023).

The existing systems are at times very scattered for both the buyer and seller. New e-book authors find it hard to pinpoint trustworthy sources to publish their work due to strict requirements laid down and lack of guidance. Additionally, there are avid e-books readers who find it hard to look for centres with many book genres in one place making it difficult to browse. In order to resolve these challenges, eBook Oasis applications provide a single platform where sales as well as purchases can occur simultaneously making it user-friendly.

In addition, education remains a bright spot in the Malaysian e-book industry's future prospects. eBook Oasis can become an important tool for schools, which can help teachers obtain and distribute educational materials electronically via e-books at ease together with other digital resources used in learning. This platform will enhance education by providing numerous learning sources, fostering interactivity and increasing students' involvement during their studies.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

In order to create eBook Oasis, it is necessary to carry out an extensive study of the present market commodities and what consumers seek. In particular, it allows for the development of products through feedback from stakeholders (Beck et al., 2001). Hence, the Agile methodology was incorporated into the Scrum system which would lead to effective and flexible project management. Incremental developments via several sprints with minor releases for entire systems are arranged by Scrum (Schwaber & Sutherland, 2020). Such attempt for getting user input just about always for new improvements is ensured by this method, which means that a platform changes alongside its customers' needs. In this digital world where things change rapidly, being able to switch quickly from one thing to another is essential in satisfying ever-changing client demands.

2.1 Agile Methodology

The agile methodology is a project management approach as well as a software development strategy that highlights flexibility, teamwork, and client input. As a result, the crew could divide the project into manageable sprints that took two to four weeks each. Each sprint would concentrate on one aspect or feature of eBook Oasis thereby making it possible for constant improvements depending on real-time feedback.

Iterative Development: In order to simplify the process of development, the entire process was divided into smaller parts or sprints that lasted an average of 2-4 weeks. With every sprint focusing on achieving a particular system persona, it also allowed provision for continuous feedback as well as improvement. In this way, eBook Oasis developed through iterations, incorporating users' feedback in refining functions and features (Schwaber & Sutherland, 2020).

Incremental Delivery: At each sprint's end, one would deliver a potentially shippable product increment to show stakeholders that actual progress was being made, whose feedback would influence eBook Oasis to meet user expectations as well as meet market trends (Ghezzi & Cavallo, 2018).

Adaptability: Because of its emphasis on adaptability, Agile enabled the development team to respond promptly when there were changes in user needs and business situations. For instance, interface and functionality changes during development came from insights derived from early user testing, thus improving experience and satisfaction (Beck et al., 2001).

Collaboration and communication: The team members were able to communicate openly and collaborate with one another at regular meetings, such as the daily stand-ups and sprint reviews. This enabled everyone to be on the same wavelength concerning project objectives, thus ensuring that problems were sorted out immediately, which led to the successful creation and launch of eBook Oasis (Schwaber & Sutherland, 2020).

Companies like Spotify and Amazon have taken on Agile methodologies for their product development processes. For example, Spotify has applied Agile practices in an effort to enhance its music streaming service by delivering new features and enhancements based on user feedback (Kniberg & Ivarsson, 2012). On the other hand, Amazon uses Agile principles to come up with innovative cloud computing services quickly that demonstrate flexibility as well as responsiveness to market demands (Denning, 2019).

2.2 Framework

Agile Scrum Process Flow

Figure 1: Agile Scrum process flow

2.3 Agile Scrum Process Flow for eBook Oasis Development

2.3.1. Product Backlog:

A Product Backlog is the first thing that is developed in eBook Oasis. This backlog includes the features, improvements and fixes that are envisaged for the application, such as simple interfaces for users, means of payments or payment gateways, searching functions and managing user profiles. The key person in this process is the product owner who will give priorities to these items depending on their significance towards achieving the bigger aim of making a full-fledged and easily operable platform for trading e-books.

2.3.2. Sprint Planning:

The development team chooses unique items from the Product Backlog which they will concentrate on during the coming sprint. For example, during the first sprint, the team may decide to focus on core functionalities of the app like setting up the database and enabling basic users' registration. Therefore, this phase's sprint goal would be to lay down a strong base for the app's infrastructure.

2.3.3. Sprint Backlog:

After sprint planning is done, tasks are added to Sprint Backlog. Therefore, tasks may include; establishing server, creating a user registration form and developing a database schema. To achieve the Sprint Goal, the team will commit themselves towards finishing these tasks by end of sprint.

2.2.4. Daily Scrum:

Daily Scrum meetings are held by development teams throughout the sprint period. Such brief daily gatherings make sure that everyone understands what has been accomplished so far; what problems have been faced; and what plans exist for today? It is imperative to keep communicating like this so that not only be able to sort out problems as they come up but also work with steady momentum throughout eBook Oasis's iterative development process.

2.2.5. Increments:

As the team works through their Sprint, they will develop Increments of the eBook Oasis app. Such increments may consist of a running registration system, an interface for user interaction or a database that is working. Each increment must meet the Definition of Done, which implies that it is complete, entirely tested and ready for evaluation or possible deployment.

2.2.6. Sprint Review:

At the end of every Sprint there is a conduct of the Sprint Review where members present to stakeholders all finished increments of eBook Oasis project. For example, the team could show how to register users and integrate databases. This allows them to collect feedback during this review so as to keep the development aligned with users' expectations as well as the business objectives.

2.2.7. Sprint Retrospective:

Following the Sprint Review, the team holds a meeting called Sprint Retrospective. In these discussions they can reflect on what went well during the Sprint and what could be improved upon in future efforts. For instance, if there were delays due to some unforeseen technical hitches, then it would be good for them to discuss how they can better anticipate such problems in future Sprints.

2.2.8. Cycle Repeat:

Every sprint has a similar rhythm, moving towards new features while improving the eBook Oasis application. Over time, the application becomes polished and ready for launch.

By using the Scrum approaches for developing eBook Oasis through iterative development that involves careful building, testing, and perfecting anywhere in the program, it introduces some flexibility as the group may change promptly to client requirements or market needs. The outcome is a complete user-oriented software which meets the requirements of buyers and vendors within the eBook industry.

3. FINDINGS

This study pointed out some of the crucial discoveries that testify to the great need for e-book oasis apps in the present market environment. In addition, eBook Oasis intends to tackle the problems that come with using traditional hardcopy books through its digital platform.

3.1 Traditional hardcover books have a number of disadvantages compared to e-books:

Accessibility and Convenience: Apart from being downloaded instantly and accessed on different media devices instantaneously, traditional paper printed versions demand some storage space and require transportation across spaces which can be tough for someone wanting to carry multiple novels while travelling or commuting (Smith & Polleck, 2023).

Cost and Affordability: e-books save on production costs alongside transport expenses whenever applicable. Thus, it becomes a difficult task for anyone interested in acquiring different types of hardbacks since most are quite expensive and hence hinder them from accessing varied ranges of literature (Gail et al., 2024).

Environmental impact: Hardcopy production leaves forests depleted and emits carbon into the atmosphere. Digital formats like e-books would however cut down on consumption of papers hence diminishing their carbon footprints eventually (Plekhanov et al., 2022).

3.2 Advantages of eBook Oasis apps:

Instantly accessible: This means having quick hands on a variety of eBooks, irrespective of their physical condition.

Inexpensive, as compared to buying which means that the traditional method of acquiring this type tends to be much more costly;

From an eco-friendly aspect, it provides a reason for people to prefer going digital rather than sticking with print books.

By integrating these elements in its services, eBook Oasis aims at creating fun out of reading through interactive features, community interactivity, enough support for both readers and writers.

4. DISCUSSION

E-book Oasis is one of the most refreshing e-book applications that serves as a complete hub for e-book buyers and sellers. Therefore, the platform ought to create seamless as well as laid-back modality for easy access, buying and selling eBooks all in one place. Specifically, eBook Oasis aims at transforming the eBook industry through addressing major weaknesses associated with print books and other digital platforms.

The worldwide eBook market has been developing consistently with greater number of readers embracing them due to their lower prices and more portability. By 2024, the global e-book market size was approximately \$14.61 billion and is likely to continue expanding particularly in the third world countries (Statista, 2023). However, it is very competitive especially where giants like Amazon Kindle, Apple Books or Google Play Books are concerned. There remains some space for more creation especially on the individualization side making eBook Oasis its exceptional point of view.

The eBook Oasis is aware of many weaknesses in printed books and current digital platforms, so it offers an appropriate answer for modern authors and readers through leveraging on advantages of digital publishing. In contrast to all other online platforms, eBook Oasis integrates an online bookstore with self-publishing software; thus, creating a space where people have discussions on e-books, rate them or recommend some to others while directly buying them as well. The inclusiveness that this platform provides makes it an irresistible offer within the world of digital literature hence ranking as one of the most ideal options in the industry.

The findings indicate that eBook Oasis has potential to revolutionize eBook market by its innovative strategy as well as comprehensiveness. Moreover, eBook Oasis presents solutions for today's writers and readers by correcting vital inadequacies found in printed books and other digital alternatives. Additionally, this platform stands out from its rivals due to the incorporation of internet bookstore into its self-publishing site which emphasizes personal touch and social interactions among users. This unparalleled invention positions eBook Oasis among other encouraging ideas in the field of digital literature.

5. CONCLUSION

In providing a simple e-book business friendly service, the eBook Oasis could fulfil the mission of bringing authors and readers together. Its mandates of low-cost informativeness accompanied with environmental consideration have enabled it to be a top-most digital publication. Therefore, eBook Oasis fits into the future of eBooks since it provides an inclusive and simple platform for both selling and buying eBooks. It is unlikely that this site will not sell more digital books because its unique features and a strong commitment to community development as well as a support system for writers cover various gaps in today's market.

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